

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPHENE NANO-PLATELETS COATED CARBON FIBER EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Carbon-fiber epoxy composites show extremely high modulus and strength in the uniaxial direction. However, they fail relatively easily under flexural loading due to the weak nature of the interface between the carbon-fiber and epoxy. In the current study, the carbon fiber has been coated with the graphene nano-platelets (GNPs) with an aim to strengthen the interface/interphase between the fiber and the matrix. GNPs were coated on the carbon fibers using spray coating process before manufacturing the final laminates through vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM). The flexural strength of the laminates has been found to improve significantly with GNP addition. Scanning electron Microscopy and optical microscopy have been used to examine the nature of interface/interphase between the fiber and the matrix as well as the mechanism of failure of the composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

High specific strength and stiffness have made carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composites one of the most commonly used material systems for a range of structural applications [1]. The various nano-particles such as carbon black, carbon nanotube (CNT), carbon nanofiber, graphene oxides, graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) etc. and many others have been successfully incorporated into the epoxy-based composites for the enhancement of the interphase/matrix properties of the composite and also reduced the cost of the fiber reinforced composites [2–6]. CNTs have proven themselves a strong participant in the matrix modification among all of them. This is because of their high aspect ratio, high specific surface area and outstanding strength and stiffness [7–9]. The only limitation for using the CNTs is their higher production cost which leads to expensive manufacturing of CNT-based multiscale composites in mass production [8]. On the other hand, graphene nano-platelets (GNPs) have great potential to be used as a nano-filler due to its high stiffness, functionality, chemical stability and cost-effectiveness. GNPs have ultrahigh surface area due to its two-dimensional structure composed of several layers of graphite nanocrystals stacked together [10,11]. The high level of stress transfer occurs across the interface of the reinforcement and matrix due to its extremely high specific surface area. Graphene-based polymer nanocomposites have better mechanical and electrical properties compared to other carbon nano-filler based polymer nanocomposites [12,13]. Graphene also provide excellent thermal and electrical conductivity than CNTs [14–16]. Qin et al. have reported an increase of 82% in flexural strength of GNP coated carbon fiber (CF) composite as compared to non-coated CF composite [6]. The carbon fiber was coated by immersing it into GNP solution. The non-coated CF composites fractographs show the pure interfacial failure however the GNP coated CF composites fractographs shows the cohesive failure mode [6]. GNP mixed epoxy carbon fiber composites showed improvement in in-plane shear modulus and strength and compressive strength [17]. H. Fukushima also reported 20% and 15% increase in interfacial shear strength and flexural strength respectively for the exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets coated CF/epoxy composites compared to control composites [18].

Literature review suggests that GNPs played an extensive role in enhancement of the properties of CFRP composites. To develop the easy process of the manufacturing of the GNP/CF/epoxy multiscale composites, the cost effective processing technique has to be used. The vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding (VARTM) technique is extensively used over the past decade for low cost high performance laminate manufacturing [19,20]. The infiltration of GNP mixed resin through carbon fiber fabrics during resin infusion process in VARTM technique is challenging. This is because of the increased viscosity of the GNP mixed resin leads to low resin fluidity. The increased viscosity also leads to filtration of GNPs at the resin inlet which leads to the GNP agglomerates and results in the nonhomogeneous distribution of GNPs [21]. Another efficient way to introduce GNPs at the interface of fiber and resin is by directly spraying the GNP fillers on to the dry fabric prior to the infusion process. The GNP fillers introduced through a spraying process have disadvantage of being loosely bonded to the fabric and can easily be washed away during the infiltration process [22]. However, the GNP distribution achieved through such a process is more uniform and compatible with composite manufacturing through VARTM process [23]. The extensive characterization of the failure modes under bending load of GNP/CF/epoxy composite manufactured by GNP spray coated CF has been rarely reported.

This study includes the manufacturing of GNP sprayed carbon fiber epoxy composites using VARTM technique. The spray coating was done by preparing the homogeneous GNP/acetone solution with the help of probe sonicator. GNP sprayed fabrics were stacked symmetrically and impregnated with the epoxy resin assisted by vacuum to manufacture the laminate. The objective of the work is the GNP deposition on the carbon fiber with spray coating and GNP/CF/epoxy laminate manufacturing through VARTM technique and then the evaluation of flexural properties of the GNP/CF/epoxy laminates and the observation of failure modes under bending load of the laminates. The work presented here has the potential to open up the new trails to fabricate GNP/CF/epoxy composites which are engineered from nano-scale to macro scale.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based 3K twill woven carbon fiber (CF) of filament diameter $7\mu\text{m}$ coated with the epoxy compatible sizing was purchased from Hindoostan Composites Solutions, Mumbai, India. The data sheet provided by the manufacturer mentioned the density, tensile strength and percentage elongation of the carbon fiber to be 1.8 g/cm^3 , 4000 MPa and 1.7% respectively. Graphene nanoplatelets powder (GNP) (average lateral dimension 5-8 μm , avg. thickness $\sim 2\text{-}5\text{ nm}$) used as nano-filler was procured from Ad-Nano Technologies Private Limited, Karnataka, India. The following details of GNPs were provided by the manufacturer: GNPs had purity $\sim 99\%$, surface area $\sim 380\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and 2-4 layers. Bisphenol-A-diglycidyl ether-based resin (Epofine-1564 epoxy) and Finehard 3486-1 as hardener were procured from Fine Finish Organics Private Ltd., Mumbai, India. The mixing ratio of epoxy resin and hardener was 100:35 by weight (according to manufacturer's data sheet). Concentrated sulfuric acid (98%) and concentrated nitric acid (69%) of EMSURE® grade were purchased from Merck Life Science Private Ltd. India and used without further purification. All materials were used as received unless otherwise stated.

2.2 Spray coating of GNPs on carbon fibers

Nanoparticles were sprayed using a Pilot Power AB-15 airbrush system manufactured by Manik Radiators Pvt. Ltd. India, connected via high performance single-piston Airbrush air compressor. 0.4 wt.% graphene nano-platelets (GNPs) were sprayed onto carbon fiber fabrics. Before the spray coating of the GNPs onto CF fabric, the GNPs were ultrasonicated in 50 ml ethanol with the help of probe-type sonicator (3 kHz, 250 Watts) for 30 minutes. The solution of the dispersed GNPs was filled in the 15ml volumetric capacity spray gun to deposit the GNPs onto both sides of the CF fabric ($320\times 320\text{ mm}$) alternatively. CF fabrics were placed onto the heating stage with a controlled temperature of 80°C during spray coating to evaporate the solvent. Eight fabrics were sprayed to manufacture the 0.4GNP laminate.

2.3 Fabrication of the GNP/CF/epoxy laminates

Vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) technique was used to prepare the composites. Eight fabrics of each set of carbon fibers (dimension 320x320 mm²) were stacked on the glass table and bagging was done which had one inlet for epoxy and one outlet for drawing the air out of the bag. The mixture of epoxy and hardener (100:35 by weight) was degassed in vacuum chamber to remove the trapped bubbles during mixing. The epoxy-hardener mixture was infused through the inlet by initiating the vacuum and passed through the flow mesh which was placed over the carbon fiber to maintain the flow of epoxy evenly in all directions. The curing of laminate was done for 24 hours at ambient temperature. Pristine laminate was the control sample in which GNP spray coating was not done. 0.4GNP laminate had 0.4 wt.% GNPs spray coating on the fabrics.

2.4 Testing and characterization

The morphology of the carbon fibers and GNPs have been investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) Hitachi S-3400 N model. JEOL JSM-7600F Field Emission Gun-Scanning Electron Microscopes (FEG-SEM) was used to study the fractured surfaces. The SEM samples of fracture surface were coated with a few nanometers layer of platinum prior to examination.

Raman spectra of carbon fibers with different treatments as well as GNPs were recorded using Raman Spectrometer (HORIBA HR 800) with 514.5 nm laser as incident light and 1-micron spot size. Each measurement was taken at 20x magnification for 120s. The spectra were acquired three times for each condition and the wavelength range was 1000-2000 cm⁻¹ for CF and 1000-3000 cm⁻¹ for GNPs.

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) (Bruker, Germany-3000 Hyperion Microscope with Vertex 80 FTIR System) was used to investigate the functional groups of carbon fibers and GNPs using powder pressed KBr pellets. The wavenumber range of the FTIR spectra was 500-4000 cm⁻¹ with a resolution of 0.2 cm⁻¹.

According to ASTM D790-02 standard, the flexural test was carried out taking three-point bending configuration by Instron model 3345 of 5 kN capacity. The test was performed at room temperature and the dimensions of the specimens were 50 mm (length) × 13.5 mm (width) × 1.8 mm (thickness). Span length was taken to be 30 mm to maintain the span to thickness ratio as 16:1. The samples were tested at a crosshead speed of 0.25 mm/min. At least four specimens per condition were tested for the flexural response.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characteristics of GNP

The SEM micrographs of as received GNPs is shown in Fig. 1a. The thin plate sheets of irregular shape of graphene have an average length of 1-3μm. Raman spectra of the GNP powder is observed to examine the graphitic structure/defects as shown in Fig. 1b. There are three characteristic peaks at 1347 cm⁻¹ (D-band), 1573cm⁻¹ (G-band) and 2708 cm⁻¹ (2D-band). D-band represents the disorder or defects in graphitic structure and the G-band represents presence of sp² carbon network or graphitic structure. 2D-band is a second order of the D-band and is also referred as an overtone of the D-band. The 2D-band is usually used to measure the number of graphene layers. D-band represents the disordered sp³ carbon and G-band represents presence of sp² carbon network or graphitic structure. The intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) of D-band (I_D) to G-band (I_G) signifies the degree of disorder in the sample [24]. The intensity ratio of GNP (I_D/I_G = 0.20) (Fig. 1b) represents a very low degree of disorder which suggest that the structure integrity is conserved and the value is similar to the previously reported intensity ratio of GNPs [25,26]. FTIR spectra of GNPs in Fig. 1c reveals the presence of C=O, C-O-C group and -OH group at 1575 cm⁻¹, 1021 cm⁻¹ and 3435 cm⁻¹ respectively. These functional groups are present on the surface as well as on edges of the GNP which improve the mechanical reinforcement in GNP/CF/epoxy composites [27–29].

Fig. 1 Characterization of GNPs (a) SEM micrograph (b) Raman spectrum and (c) FTIR spectrum

3.2 Characteristics of carbon fibers

The morphology of the as received carbon fiber i.e. Pristine-CF is shown in Fig. 2a. Narrow longitudinal grooves have been observed on the surface of the fibers fabricated using the wet spinning process of PAN-precursors [30]. The average diameter of the five fibers with 20 data points was calculated and found $\sim 7.2 \mu\text{m}$. Raman spectra of Pristine-CF is shown in Fig. 2b. The spectra range of 1000 to 2000 cm^{-1} has been taken into consideration due to two major peaks around 1350-1360 cm^{-1} and 1585-1595 cm^{-1} . The intensity ratio (I_D/I_G) of pristine-CF is 0.963. This represents the higher disorder in graphitic structure of pristine CF. Fig. 2c shows the FT-IR spectra of carbon fibers and represents the presence of functional groups on the surface of carbon fiber: carbonyl group C=O ($\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), C-O-C ($\sim 1050 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), hydrocarbon group -CH ($\sim 2920 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and hydroxyl group -OH (3430 cm^{-1}).

Fig. 2 Pristine-CF (a) SEM micrograph (b) Raman spectrum and (c) FTIR spectrum

3.3 Flexural properties

Three-point bending or flexural loading applies both tensile and compressive stresses on different parts of the specimen and hence is a great way to determine the behavior of composites under these stresses. The four samples' average data of the flexural test were collected according to ASTM D790-02 standard. The two curves, representative of each condition laminate stress-strain curves under flexural loading, are shown in Fig. 3a and the data for flexural stress and modulus is plotted in Fig. 3b. The flexural modulus of 0.4GNP laminate is 20% higher than pristine laminate. This enhancement in modulus attributes the stiffening effect of rigid GNPs. Lee et al. reported the Young's modulus and the intrinsic strength of graphene as 1TPa and $\sim 30 \text{ GPa}$ [15]. Even if the oxides are present in GNPs (in our case), there can be an increase in stiffness and strength of the fiber-epoxy interface. The flexural strength of 0.4GNP laminate shows an increase of 20% compared to pristine laminate. The flexural strain at maximum stress shows a decrease of 6% in 0.4GNP laminate compared to pristine laminate. The pristine laminate shows the flexural strength value of 629 MPa and the flexural strength was found to be enhanced as 760 MPa for 0.4GNP laminates. Both the GNP addition and the presence of hydroxyl group on GNPs and CFs played an important role in the improvement of flexural strength and modulus. This signifies the role of GNPs as a nano-filler in improvement of the interfacial interactions in fiber-matrix.

Fig. 3 Flexural test results of GNP/carbon fiber/epoxy composites

3.4 Fracture characteristics

The failure of fiber reinforced composites under bending load generally occurs due to tensile load at the bottom, compressive load at the top. Delamination occurs under bending load when the plies of the fibers gets separated due to weak interfacial interactions or severe shear loading [31]. Micro-buckling generally occurs under compressive loading and it could transform into kink bands. The practical kink band can be seen in fractured surface of 0.4GNP laminates, as shown in Fig. 4. This indicates the presence of kink band and the fiber micro-buckling under compressive loading. However, the tensile failure in bending is uncommon due to high ratio of tensile strength to compressive strength of carbon fiber composites.

Fig. 4 SEM micrograph showing kink band of fracture surface of 0.4GNP laminate

The optical micrographs of front side of the flexural test specimens after the rapid load drop are shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. Pristine laminate in Fig. 5b shows the kink band and the localized fiber fracture at the compression side of the laminate. The fiber failure, transverse crack and delamination can be seen at tension side in Fig. 5c. The fiber failure successively propagates the large delamination at the bottom of the pristine laminate due to the incompatibility of straining of the fibers with the epoxy. Delamination shows the weak interaction of the fibers with the epoxy which reduces the load carrying capacity of the laminates. No fiber failure is observed in 0.4GNP laminate at the tension side, as shown in Fig. 6b. However, the fiber failure, transverse crack and kink band can also be seen at the compression side of 0.4GNP laminate. The through thickness transverse crack propagation can be seen in 0.4GNP laminate (Fig. 6a) indicating the brittle nature of the laminate [32].

Fig. 5 Optical images of the pristine laminate failed under flexural loading (a) through thickness view (b) compressive side magnified view, (c) tensile side magnified

Fig. 6 Optical images of the 0.4GNP laminate failed under flexural loading (a) through thickness view (b) magnified view as indicated by box in (a)

Fig. 7 Fracture surface morphology of flexural test specimens: longitudinal fibers (a) Pristine, (b) 0.4 GNP; transverse fibers (c) Pristine, (d) 0.4GNP

The morphology of fractured surfaces of flexural test specimens is shown in Fig. 7. The black and white arrows in micrographs signify the epoxy and carbon fiber respectively. Fig. 7a shows fracture surface of pristine laminate indicating neat fibers with low amount of epoxy. In case of 0.4GNP (Fig. 7b), a significant amount of epoxy is adhered on or near to the fiber periphery which indicates the good adhesion of the epoxy with the fiber surface. The less density of the adhered epoxy can be clearly seen in the transverse fibers of the pristine laminate (Fig. 7c) compared to 0.4GNP laminate (Fig. 7d). The debonding in between fiber and epoxy is also shown 0.4GNP laminates indicated by white dash line in Fig. 7c. However, this debonding is not seen in 0.4GNP laminate which indicates the strong fiber-epoxy interactions. In the summary of 0.4GNP laminates, there is effect of GNP coating which leads to the stronger interfacial adhesion between the fiber and epoxy. The fracture surface morphology agrees with the flexural test results shown in Fig. 3.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The study was carried out aiming to manufacture the GNP/CF/epoxy multiscale composite using spray coating of GNPs onto CF and VARTM technique. The higher flexural strength and modulus was achieved for 0.4wt.% GNP coated laminate compared to pristine laminates. The flexural response and the failure mechanism of the GNP/CF/epoxy composites is understood with the help of optical and SEM micrographs.

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